

Agroecology for Europe (AE4EU)

Deliverable report D4.4 – Agroecology Training Guidelines

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Background

This report links principles and process of training activities with a focus on agroecological transition and in the context of the work done by the European Coordination Via Campesina¹ (ECVC). Due to representing small and medium scale farmers' organisations ECVC has a strong focus on peasant agroecology and plays an important role in disseminating knowledge concerning agroecological transition.

The main objective of this Deliverable is to provide guidelines that allow to develop, implement and evaluate further training sessions targeted at agroecology transition. The design of the Training Guideline and the topics of the curriculum is the result of the needs expressed during the workshop implemented in Brussels, Belgium on 13-14 March 2023 and of the feedback received by participants during and after 3 training programmes in the Netherlands, in France and in the UK with support of three farmers' organisations. Those also were included in the Guideline as peasant agroecology training programme examples. Insights distilled from these experiences are combined with outcomes from other projects to formulate guidelines for transformative agroecology learning. The Deliverable contains guidelines and a curriculum based on outcomes of international educational projects, thereby linking training on agroecology with other EU funded projects with a focus on education such as SUSPLUS² and NextFood³.

The guideline and the curriculum provided in this Deliverable are based on theoretical knowledge, practical experience and exchanges that should be considered for efficient training on agroecological transition. Furthermore, the guidelines emphasise a strong focus on the grassroots level and an important role of action learning, Peasant to Peasant (P2P) methodology and the "*diálogo de saberes*" or "dialogue between ways of knowing" as an educational approach with different practical activities (meetings, seminars, individual readings, frontal lectures, experience exchanges, field visits, etc.). The Deliverable proposes to use frontal lectures, to implement them [MOU1] [MOU2] at all levels with proper content, language, [MOU3] and to combine them with action learning and Peasant to Peasant (P2P) methodologies considering principles of horizontalism, peer-to-peer and participation.

This training guideline follows the perspective of the ECVC's vision on peasant agroecology as an open process, which allows the peasants to put their knowledge into practice using the 'learning by doing' methodology, and to reinforce it through collective work and the relationship with the environment. The multiplication of knowledge is made possible by the creation of a network of promoters by training of trainers who will replicate the experiences in their own

1 <https://www.eurovia.org/>

2 <https://surplus.eu>

3 <https://www.nextfood-project.eu/>

territories. This positive and proactive relationship with the environment enables them to adapt their production model to environmental and climatic conditions, to increase the production capacities and methods to implement the resistance and enhance their resilience and ecological, socio-economic and cultural sustainability of farming systems by agroecological peasant farming.

1. Introduction

One of the project partners, ECVC, is a confederation of unions and organisations of peasant farmers, small and medium-scale farmers, and agricultural workers across Europe. ECVC is composed of 31 national and regional peasant farmer organisations from 21 European countries. For the AE4EU project ECVC has developed and carried out three training programmes in agroecology in order to foster the agroecological transition in Europe during the AE4EU project timeline. The training programmes were designed to reflect the Nyéléni Declaration of the international Forum for Agroecology (2015)⁴ on learning agroecology and also ECVC's vision on peasant agroecology⁵.

ECVC defines peasant agroecology as a way of life, working with nature and not against it towards sustainable agriculture, and considers training and learning activities as an important process for agroecology transition. Agroecology offers solutions to the major environmental, social, economic and political challenges we are facing today. It is a living practice, as well as a science and a socio-political movement, built and fostered by people over thousands of years. According to ECVC, training and learning is an infinite process of permanent production and dissemination of new knowledge that comes from sharing different opinions and ideas, and from meeting new ideas with realities. The content of this Guide was further validated through a round of consultations with the AE4EU Work Package 4 partners.

Agroecology, due to its knowledge-intensive character, combines traditional, indigenous, peasant and experiential knowledges with elements of modern ecological, social and agronomic science, creating a dialogue of wisdoms from which principles for designing and managing biodiversified and resilient farms are derived; and vocational training are widely used in different countries for agroecological transition and for fostering agroecology^{6 7 8 9}.

Thus, in order to provide an adequate interpretation of reality, peasant farmers movements and organisations who have a deep knowledge of the ecosystem, as they live within it and interact with nature, are important actors for the training that propose and take on the political strategic

4 <https://www.foodsovereignty.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/Download-declaration-Agroecology-Nyeleni-2015.pdf>

5 <https://www.eaken.eurovia.org/peasant-agroecology-according-to-ecvc/>

6 Pimbert, M., Moeller, N. I., Singh, J., & Anderson, C. (2021). Agroecology. In Oxford Research Encyclopedias Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190854584.013.298>

7 FAO. (2019). Scaling up agroecology to achieve the sustainable development goals. In Proceedings of the 2nd FAO International Symposium on Agroecology. Rome: FAO.

8 Deguine, Jean & Gloanec, Caroline & Laurent, Philippe & Ratnadass, Alain & Aubertot, Jean-Noël. (2017). Agroecological Crop Protection. 10.1007/978-94-024-1185-0.

⁹ Migliorini, P., & Lieblein, G. (2016). Facilitating transformation and competence development in sustainable agriculture university education: an experiential and action oriented approach. *Sustainability*, 8(12), 1243.

direction with a higher probability of success and of attaining both immediate and strategic goals ¹⁰.

Transformative agroecology learning, a collective strategy for food system transformation, is based on four key characteristics or qualities: horizontalism; *diálogo de saberes* (transdisciplinary); combining practical and political knowledge; and building social movement networks (Anderson et al. 2019). During the last decade several educational projects funded by the EU (e.i. SUSPLUS, NextFood), focused on improving higher and vocational education in sustainable agriculture and agroecology, have generated important insights for transformative learning. According to Anderson et al.¹¹ insights from transformative agroecology learning in many cases are not systematised.

This Training Guideline works towards systematising insights and experiences in and provides guidelines for transformative agroecology learning, to improve the efficiency of agroecological training programmes across Europe.

¹⁰ <https://agroecologia-socla2015.net/>

¹¹ Anderson, C.R., Maughan, C. & Pimbert, M.P. Transformative agroecology learning in Europe: building consciousness, skills and collective capacity for food sovereignty. *Agric Hum Values* 36, 531–547 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-018-9894-0>

2. Agroecology Training Guidelines

The Aim of This Guideline

The aim of this guidelines is to provide space for peasants to collectively develop knowledge and practical skills in areas of peasant agroecology in order to promote sustainable agricultural food production systems across Europe and beyond, while creating a stronger network of peasants with a deeper understanding of their rights and have an amplified voice towards the positive change they want to see. The starting point in developing a training programme is the planning process. According to the lessons learned after the workshop in Brussels, selecting a target audience, determining the goals and the content of the training is the first step in planning a training.

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The Learning Objectives:

To improve the general literacy around peasant agroecology and standardise the understanding across peasants at all levels and also other actors in food systems.

1. To reorient food production systems; demystify myths around industrialised food systems while empowering peasants with their rights for food production and food sovereignty.
2. To spread peasant agroecology as a transdisciplinary initiative beyond practice.
3. To instigate food systems initiatives through development of farm and community-based food systems plans to support the transition to peasant agroecology
4. To build a strong network of peasants who are knowledgeable of their practices and can speak with one voice to advocate for global transition to peasant agroecology.
5. To initiate training programmes focusing women to strengthen their capacity and roles.

The Learning Outcomes

Upon completion of the programme, the participants should be able to:

1. Understand and reach the level for advocacy of what peasant agroecology is and what it is not.
2. Identify the principles of peasant agroecology
3. Justify the urgent need for transition towards peasant agroecology and food sovereignty.
4. Understand how to build a balanced, equitable and fair food system through agroecology.
5. Appreciate the socio-ecological and economic values of traditional peasant knowledge systems in agroecological settings.
6. Promote agro-bio diversification of farms and their role in financial and farm autonomy.
7. Build and amplify social movements and alliances on sustainable food systems
8. Define their and other actors' roles in building a balanced, equitable and transparent food system.
9. Develop plans to practise peasant agroecology at farm and community level.
10. Properly use training guidelines to develop training programmes based on their needs.

11. Be the resource people to transmit information on existing policy and legislations for agroecology in order to do advocacy for a better agroecological transition

The Target Group

Training programmes can target farmers, farmer leaders and trainers, community leaders/organisers, leaders and facilitators of the networks for food and agriculture systems, new farmers/new entrants, youth, women or a mix. They can also include producers in processing, short food chain actors such as distributors, cooperatives, networks, activists and/or researchers. However, any training aimed at agroecological transformation should always put farmers in the centre as the key actors.

An important target group to consider are (urban and rural) activists. Activists may have much information and are committed to make changes in the rural world but their understanding and experience with the reality and practices of rural life and production is limited. Engagements between activists and farmers in a training setting can contribute to filling these knowledge gaps while offering valuable political lessons to the participants.

Local or regional policy makers are not included as a target audience very often. Nevertheless, including them in another role can be useful to learn more about the political challenges and opportunities farmers are facing. Local policy makers can for example be included through an excursion to the municipality or to an event for municipalities. Dialogue or discussions between participating farmers and policy makers on key policies could generate lessons that support the aim of the training. Involving representatives from local governments, municipalities as a speaker at the training can create real life discussion and problem-solving spaces.

Once the target audience has been decided, the educational activities should be selected and planned. Planning of the training activities includes setting following elements of the training:

- Learning Objectives (right and clearly formulated), objective determines all training activities and audience
- Discussed topics and curriculum depend on the stated objective and selected audience (relevance, quality of the content)
- Training approaches: The methodology and the pedagogical approach
- Trainers based on the defined goals and a contents
- Trainers/Facilitators

Planning process should include a clear agenda which includes methodology, objectives and outcomes along with the resource documents for each session.

Potential challenges that should be taken into consideration during planning process of the training activities:

- Diversity: Ensuring spaces for women, gender and other diversities, and youth,
- Distance: Ensuring both virtual and in-person training programmes and creating easy access to the training materials.

- Farmers' and landworkers' time: Timing should be programmed in advance with consultation with farmers in relation to farm work and seasonal work-load
- Level of knowledge: Taking into consideration of the participants with different levels of knowledge and experience

How to use the training guidelines

The training program recognises that there are variations in operational areas and practices within peasant agroecology. Therefore, instead of providing an exhaustive list of practices for each section, the program outline serves as a guide. The facilitators/trainers delivering the program have the responsibility of identifying and extracting different practices from the participants and allowing for practical sharing of experiences. They should focus on learning from the best practices within each section while staying within the framework of the main learning areas.

This training guideline follows the perspective of the ECVC as peasant agroecology is an open process, which allows the peasants to put their knowledge into practice using the 'learning by doing' methodology, and to reinforce it through collective work and the relationship with the environment. The multiplication of knowledge is made possible by the creation of a network of promoters by training of trainers who will replicate the experiences in their own territories. This positive and proactive relationship with the environment enables them to adapt their production model to environmental and climatic conditions, to increase the production capacities and methods to implement the resistance and enhance their resilience and ecological, socio-economic and cultural sustainability of farming systems by agroecological peasant farming.

To ensure the training is practical, facilitators/trainers should consider the participants' expectations regarding learning peasant agroecology and their experiences within the group regarding specific concepts. This information can be used as a basis for selecting practical elements that align with the respective sections of the training program. By incorporating the participants' expectations and experiences, the training can be tailored to their specific needs and foster a more engaging and effective learning environment.

3. Training Methodology

It is important to note that this composite programme serves as a guide in the training of peasant agroecology to peasants, small-scale farmers and other actors in the sustainable food systems. This programme describes and outlines the content that guides in a peasant agroecology training programme. The Guideline proposes participatory methodologies such as Peasant to Peasant (P2P) which allows farmers to find innovative solutions to the challenges they may face. This also creates a trusted space for horizontal communication and knowledge sharing among peasants. The methodology includes case studies, discussion circles, visual material, group and individual activities in and out of the classroom.

It is important to note that the minimum contact hours between the facilitators and the participants should be not less than 16 hours for consideration of completion. Facilitators should create a supportive and inclusive environment that promotes effective cross-pollination and learning among participants, fostering the safe sharing of experiences and visions. Each session includes exercises and participatory techniques.

In order to achieve the objectives of this programme, facilitators must use, but not limited to the following approaches in training the participants:

Action Learning

The guidelines emphasise a strong focus on the grassroots level and an important role of action learning as an educational approach with different practical activities (meetings, seminars, individual readings, frontal lectures, experience exchanges, field visits, etc.). The Deliverable proposes to use frontal lectures, to implement them [MOU1] [MOU2] at all levels with proper content, language,[MOU3] and to combine them with action learning methodologies considering principles of horizontalism, peer-to-peer and participation.

An action learning approach that has made a shift from theory towards “world” as the starting point for the learning process (Lieblein at al. 2010; Biesta, 2022) was used as a basis for training activities which included following:

- Practical information concerning agroecology
- Dialogue between the stakeholders
- Movement building

“Peasant to Peasant” (P2P) methodology and the Diálogo de Saberes

Peasant to Peasant (P2P), as the grassroots social methodology is the most effective way found to date, and of Altieri that rural social movements hold the key¹². P2P methodology highlights the importance of horizontal communication and knowledge sharing among peasants. P2P emphasises the idea that peasants themselves are the primary agents of innovation and knowledge exchange. It recognizes that peasants have a deep understanding of their local environments, including the land, seed, climate, and socio-historic conditions, which influences their agricultural practices and techniques. This methodology seeks to harness and promote this rich peasant knowledge, which is tightly connected to the specific territory and cultural heritage.

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The concept of "diálogo de saberes" or "dialogue between ways of knowing" in the Peasant-to-Peasant methodology is an approach that recognizes and values the diverse ways in which individuals understand and interact with the world. It goes beyond the traditional notion of education as a one-way transmission of knowledge and emphasises the importance of dialogue and mutual learning.

Rather than viewing learners as passive recipients of information, the Peasant-to-Peasant methodology, by using the approach of diálogo de saberes, sees them as active participants and agents of their own learning. It encourages learners to engage in a process of discovery, where they actively contribute their own knowledge, experiences, and perspectives while also being open to learning from others.

The emphasis on dialogue in this methodology is crucial. Instead of simply delivering knowledge in a hierarchical manner, the aim is to foster an inclusive and respectful conversation where different ways of knowing can be shared, questioned, and enriched. Through dialogue, participants can challenge preconceived notions, develop critical thinking skills, and collectively construct new knowledge and understanding.

Overall, the Peasant-to-Peasant methodology and the concept of "diálogo de saberes" promote a collaborative and transformative learning process that recognizes the importance of diverse knowledges and actively involves learners in their own formation.

The new collective understandings, meanings and knowledges may form the basis for collective actions of resistance and construction of new processes¹³.

12 Peter Rosset, Valentín Val, Lia Pinheiro Barbosa & Nils McCune (2019): Agroecology and La Via Campesina II. Peasant agroecology schools and the formation of a sociohistorical and political subject, Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems, DOI: 10.1080/21683565.2019.1617222

13 María Elena Martínez-Torres & Peter M. Rosset (2014) Diálogo de saberes in La Vía Campesina: food sovereignty and agroecology, The Journal of Peasant Studies, 41:6,

The organisations that make up LVC have increasingly developed agroecological formación processes aimed at accelerating historical transitions to food sovereignty.

The fact that agroecology is based on applying principles in ways that depend on local realities means that the local knowledge and ingenuity of farmers must necessarily take a front seat in this understanding.

The tasks and roles of Trainers/Facilitators

It is important to consider to set-up a training team and preparing for a training session.

1. Importance to build a training team: The training team should be involved in all stages of the training, including preparation, implementation, and post-training activities. This ensures consistency and continuity throughout the process.
2. Trainers as facilitators: Depending on the duration of the training, it is recommended to have two facilitators who can alternate in leading and supporting the training. This helps maintain engagement and prevents fatigue and mistakes.
3. Support staff: Support staff play a crucial role in preparing training materials, handling logistics such as photocopying documents, and assisting the facilitators during the training.
4. Documentation: Assigning a person to document the training through note-taking and photography is important for capturing key information and preparing a training report.
5. Reviewing the learning guide: The trainer or training team should review the learning guide in collaboration with the organisation involved in the training. This ensures a common understanding of the methodology, materials, and background for each session.
6. Pre-training preparations: The trainer or training team should define the roles and responsibilities for each session in advance. They should make a list of necessary preparations, required materials, responsibilities, and timing.
7. Rehearsal: Allocating one day for a rehearsal before the training allows the trainer or training team to walk through and practise each session. This ensures smooth delivery and identifies any gaps in materials or processes.
8. Technical background and facilitation: The trainer or training team should allocate time to understand the technical background covered in the sessions and to enhance their facilitation skills.

By following these recommendations, the training team can effectively prepare for and deliver a training session, resulting in a more successful and impactful learning experience.

4. Peasant Agroecology Training Programme Curriculum

Each training programme should organise the logistics and the methodology team in advance. Trainers/facilitators for different sessions, room plan, field trip/work and the materials/tools to be used during the sessions and the room design should be defined before the training programme.

ACTIVITY/ TOPIC	LEARNING OBJECTIVES	LEARNING OUTCOMES - PARTICIPANTS WILL BE ABLE TO:	RESOURCES/BACKGROUND DOCUMENTS	METHODOLOGY
What is peasant agroecology?	Understand peasant agroecology is not only a sustainable farming practice but considers the relationship between people, plants, animals and their environment.	Be able to present the ECVC approach to peasant agroecology, Nyeleni Agroecology Declaration and FAO and HLPE principles of agroecology and the food sovereignty concept of La Via Campesina.	Peasant Agroecology Declaration of ECVC (2014): https://www.eurovia.org/publications/agroecology-transforming-society-through-food-production-and-the-peasant-struggle/	Participants to work in small groups comparing various ECVC, FAO, HLPE, + other sources)
	Understand peasant agroecology asks for systemic change and is a political movement.	<u>Define Agroecology Principles:</u> + Environmental Dimension to Agroecology + Political, Social and Cultural Dimensions of Agroecology + Economic Dimension of Agroecology	Peasant Agroecology According to ECVC (2022): https://www.eurovia.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Agroecology_EN.pdf	Create small posters about what agroecology means to them.

	<p>Understand what is food sovereignty and the relation between food sovereignty and agroecology</p>		<p>Nyéléni Declaration of the international forum for agroecology: https://www.foodsovereignty.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/Download-declaration-Agroecology-Nyeleni-2015.pdf</p>	<p>Aim is for the group to reflect and share different perspectives of agroecology to each other</p>
	<p>Understand the basic concepts, structures and glossary around agroecology, food sovereignty, climate justice, peasants' rights</p>		<p>FAO “The 10 elements of agroecology guiding the transition to sustainable food and agriculture systems”: https://www.fao.org/3/i9037en/i9037en.pdf</p>	
	<p>Understand that in order to strengthen organisations the work should be done through collective horizontal processes, not individualised projects</p>		<p>HLPE - Agroecological and other innovative approaches for sustainable agriculture and food systems that enhance food security and nutrition: https://www.fao.org/3/ca5602en/ca5602en.pdf</p>	
	<p>Understand that building capacity to struggle and transform, not to conform, is key.</p>		<p>Food Sovereignty: https://www.eurovia.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/FOOD_EN.pdf</p>	

	<p>Understand that question and transform structures, instead of reproducing them is vital for transformation of the society</p>		<p>Food Sovereignty Now! An In-Depth Guide: https://www.eurovia.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/FINAL-EN-FoodSov-A5-rev6.pdf</p>	
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<p>Introduction to 'AE practices'</p>	<p>Understand and exchange on Ground-cover management, integrated crop-livestock, sustainable viticulture, integrated pest management, agroforestry, biodynamic agriculture, plant-plant interaction, regenerative agriculture, permaculture, Synergistic Agriculture, reduced tillage, virtuous farming techniques, such as, water and soil conservation, farmers' seed systems, crop mixing, rotation and diversification, the release of beneficial insects and the use of manual labour and animal traction</p>	<p>Analyse the practices and able to define and choose the best-fit practices</p>		
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Protecting and developing biodiversity on the farm - INTRODUCTION	Understand agro biodiversity in its different forms as the basis of cohabiting and survival on earth	Be able to defend agroecological diversity and approach to life:		
		Crop, animal, seed, soil diversity, Biodiversity conservation technologies, GMOs, genomic techniques and their impacts on agriculture and life		
		Ability to summarise the challenges of preserving domestic biodiversity (food sovereignty, dependence on inputs, adaptation to the land and to climate change, etc.)		

Soil health, building fertility and crop rotation	Understand the importance of soil organisms and soil structure to the health of the soil	Determine texture and structure of soil through visual and touch assessments	PESTICIDES OUT ! https://www.eurovia.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/ECVC_Out-Pesticides-Brochure_EN_2018.pdf	
	Identify different soil types based on the texture and structure and literacy of soil analysis on the agroecological farm.	Define the role and importance of organic matter in soil (water holding capacity, aeration, nutrient	Roots of Resilience - Land Policy for an Agroecological Transition in Europe: https://www.eurovia.org/wp-	

	bank, cation exchange capacity- CAC)	content/uploads/2021/02/rootsofresilience_online-light2.pdf	
Understand soil, plant-water Relations (Understanding the complex relationship of the three elements)	Identify potential deficiencies by observing the plant		
Understand the role and impact of different types of cultivation	Demonstrate the processes behind building and maintaining an effective composting system		
Be aware of different methods for improving soil fertility in enhancing soil	Identify crop families to plan and carry successful rotations		
Know the products used for "plant protection" and which result from synthetic chemistry, synthetic biology, and/ or which enter the field of nanotechnologies.	Discuss soil and water conservations, water harvesting techniques and field water management, control of run-off, water pollution		
	Outline nutrient recycling and improved efficiency of ecological processes as the bedrock for productive Agroecosystems.		

		Demonstrate ecological management of pest, weeds and soil fertility for increased productivity with minimum to no external inputs.		
		Recognise climate change mitigation through systematic management of carbon.		

Distribution of Power	Understand the power and control on the food systems - Corporate capture	Demonstrates that systems such as patriarchy, class and racism can affect participation decision-making mechanism in the communities, farms and organisations	Embracing Rural Diversity: Genders and Sexualities in the Peasant Movement: https://www.eurovia.org/publications/embracing-rural-diversity-genders-and-sexualities-in-the-peasant-movement/	
	Recognition of the role of women, youth and children in decision making and in bringing about positive change			
	Understand our diverse gender and sexual diversities and identities as political identities			

FIELD WORK	Soil Sampling and Soil Nutritional composition Analysis – (application of lime or ash for pH correction, application rate of manure)
	Basal Dressing techniques (Manure treatment, Compost, Vermicompost, Biofertilizer, Biochar, Green manuring)
	Top Dressing (Liquid manures, Fermented Biofertilizer)
	Soil organic matter and its role in soil physical and chemical properties.
	Soil fertility management approaches for increasing soil organic matter: mulching, green manuring and cover cropping, etc.

Peasant seed systems and Cultivated biodiversity	Understand peasant seeds, peasants' rights to seeds and their seed autonomy	Explain the societal stakes of the preservation of cultivated biodiversity and the right of farmers to sow part of their harvest	Key documents of ECVC: Seeds and Genetically Modified Organisms (GMOs): https://www.eurovia.org/working-groups/seeds-and-genetically-modified-organisms-gmos/	
	Know UNDROP AND ITPGRFA: Legal recognition of the rights of peasants to seeds	Know how to make people think about selection schemes, the impact of cultivated varieties on the production system, the interest in developing seed autonomy on one's farm in connection with other farmers in the area.	Seed Stories Fighting Against the Privatisation of Life: https://viacampesina.org/en/publication-seed-stories-fighting-against-the-privatisation-of-life/	
	Understand Seed Rights and Legislation at national, regional and international level	Present the main obstacles to the use of farm-saved seeds and to recall the rights of farmers in this matter	United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Peasants and Other People Working in Rural Areas: https://www.eurovia.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/UNDROP-Book-of-Illustrations-1-EN-1-Web.pdf	
	Understand the legal frameworks which exclude and criminalise peasant seed systems	Identify and summarise the UPOV Convention: an international framework developed for and by the industrial seed system and the European legislation on seeds marketing violates the rights of peasants to exchange and sell their seeds.	ITRPGRFA: https://www.fao.org/plant-treaty/en/	

	<p>Knowledge of the regulatory framework for seeds and GMOs: intellectual property law, patent law;</p>	<p>Share the economic environment of seeds: main seed companies and industries, strategy of industrialists to impose new GMOs etc.</p>	<p>https://www.eurovia.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Publication-Incorporating-Peasants-Rights-to-Seeds-in-European-Law_EN.pdf</p>	
		<p>Present the issues at stake in the fight against old and new GMOs</p>		
	<p>Know the main obstacles to the use by farmers of their own seeds: use of the F1 hybridization technique by the seed industry, European seed and intellectual property law (patents, plant variety certificates etc.)</p>	<p>Transmit at different levels of precision the technical, legal, economic and political knowledge of the fight against GMOs and the privatisation of life.</p>		
	<p>Understand different techniques of genome modification, both old (cell fusion, mutagenesis, transgenesis etc.) and new (in vitro cell multiplication, directed mutagenesis etc.)</p>	<p>Formulate proposals to develop seed autonomy on a farm scale.</p>		
		<p>Define ECVC regulatory frameworks dealing with commercial seeds and with peasant seed systems and to rephrase the demands and requests of ECVC for a coherent European Regulatory Framework</p>		

		Ability to summarise the challenges of preserving cultivated biodiversity (food sovereignty, dependence on inputs, genetic homogenisation and health, fragility, etc.)		
		Good understanding of the societal challenges of preserving domestic biodiversity.		
		Know how to highlight the advantages of hardiness and adaptation of plants to the local soil, climate and agronomic environment		

Animal Biodiversity on farm	Know how to analyse and explain how selection based solely on the criterion of productivity per animal is detrimental to other selective advantages and constrains the production system and breeding practices.	Analyse the genetic selection issues at farm level and identify the relevant selection criteria (performance, longevity, hardiness etc.)	ECVC publication: Livestock farming in the European Union: supporting an ambitious transition to peasant farming: https://www.eurovia.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/ECVC-2023-ENG-Livestock.pdf	
	Know how to highlight the advantages of hardiness and the	Know the legal, technical and commercial constraints that	Booklet “La biodiversité animale à la ferme” - Confédération paysanne	

	adaptation of animals to the specificities of the territory.	hinder the development of farmer breeding.		
	Know how to bring out the distinction between individual genetic performance and adaptation to the system as a whole (environment, breeding practices etc.)	Know the farmers' practices that allow the development of the autonomy of the breeding system and the increase of genetic diversity (mass selection practices, decision-making autonomy, etc.)	Global Plan of Action for Animal Genetic Resources – Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) – 2007	
	Know the origin of pyramidal animal selection and its consequences on the decline of genetic diversity	Demonstrate how to direct people towards actors who are involved in preserving domestic biodiversity (breeder groups, exchange networks, associations, etc.).	Wilderswil Declaration on Livestock Diversity – La Via Campesina: https://viacampesina.org/en/wilderswil-declaration-on-livestock-diversity/	
	Master the issues of genetic impoverishment of livestock and the protection of small breeds			
	Know the technical, commercial and administrative constraints of selection			

Technological Autonomy	Developing technological autonomy on a farm scale	Express the evolution of farmers' relations with technology throughout history	Atelier paysan exhibition "Machines et bâtiments agricoles libres": https://www.latelierpaysan.org/No-s-expositions	
	Strengthening advocacy capacity	Illustrate how agro-equipment constrains production systems and technical itineraries	Campagnes Solidaire n°361, Folder "L'autonomie technologique pour l'agriculture paysanne": https://www.confederationpaysanne.fr/sites/1/cs/documents/CS%20361%20leger.pdf	
	Support critical thinking and analysis on high technology and digitalisation in food and agriculture systems	Recognise the links between technological development and indebtedness, land restructuring, work rationalisation and energy dependence	The Atelier paysan plea for technological sovereignty: https://www.latelierpaysan.org/Plaidoyer-souverainete-technologique-des-paysans	
	Analyse the imposition of technological and infrastructural regime centred on extracting maximum production from the land by states and large corporations	Acquired new construction techniques and is able to mobilise them to increase the technological autonomy of their farm.	ECVC Peasant Agroecology in Eastern Europe and Central Asia - PACE Future technologies and food sovereignty publication: https://www.eurovia.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/PACE-Future-technologies-and-FS.pdf	

	Build on the false ‘feed the world’ narrative of industrialised farming and digitalisation	Presents a critical analysis towards digital technologies on their farm and in society.		
	Understand classification of 4IR technologies: Digitalisation, Automation and sensing, Molecular manipulation and Natural systems modification	Present peasant technologies used in agriculture and articulate agroecology as innovation for food sovereignty		

5. Guidelines On Evaluation Of Training Session

In order to receive more detailed feedback, evaluation of the training should be provided by both trainers and the participants.

It is suggested a closure of the training should be first conducted by the trainer/facilitator. Make closing remarks for the training session: Take a few moments to summarise the key points covered during the training session. Highlight the main takeaways and emphasise their significance. Express your gratitude to the participants for their engagement and participation throughout the session.

For conducting the final reflection, the purpose of the session should be explained and the objective of the training programme should be reminded. It is important to make the group be open in their reflections. Encouraging the participants to explore how they can effectively incorporate these ideas into their own specific situations or contexts is also important in the closure and before the evaluation of the programme. These would facilitate a meaningful and interactive reflection process that allows participants to consolidate their learning, gain insights, and develop strategies for applying their newfound knowledge and skills.

Material: Evaluation Questionnaire

Evaluation by trainers

Table 1. Matrix for evaluation of training on agroecological transition by trainers

N	Questions	Evaluation
1	How would you evaluate defined objectives of the training?	1-not clear, 2- somewhat clear, 3- moderately clear, 4-very clear
2	How would you evaluate achieved goals (increased awareness of agroecological transition) of the performed training?	1- not achieved, 2- somewhat achieved, 3- moderately achieved, 4- achieved
3	How would you evaluate the content introduced during the training (its usefulness, appropriate focus, specific interest)	not interesting/useful/appropriate (1) - interesting/useful/appropriate (4)
4	How would you evaluate the time allowed for this training?	1-not sufficient time, 2- somewhat sufficient time, 3- moderately sufficient time, 4- sufficient time
5	How would you evaluate the location for the training activity?	1-not comfortable, 2- somewhat comfortable, 3- sufficiently comfortable, 4- very comfortable
6	How would you evaluate the training performance (process) from a participation point of view?	1- not participative, 2- somewhat participative, 3- moderately participative, 4

		– Very participative (*participation of the trainees in training activities)
7	How would you evaluate the methodology/training approach?	1-not appropriate, 2- somewhat appropriate, 3- moderately appropriate, 4- very appropriate
8	How would you evaluate the training outcomes received by the participants (received knowledge/practices/level of capacity building/encouragement)?	1- low, 2- moderate, 3- high, 4- very high
9	How would you evaluate coherence of training activities with your expectations and needs?	1-not coherent, 2- somewhat coherent, 3- moderately coherent, 4- very coherent
10	How would you evaluate the training programme and space for sharing experience and ideas?	1-not appropriate, 2- somewhat appropriate, 3- moderately appropriate, 4- very appropriate

Open-ended questions:

- 1) What can be improved for future training programmes/workshops and other comments/suggestions?
- 2) What do you think was missing during the training?
- 3) In terms of content, which components need further elaboration?

Evaluation by participants

In order to triangulate evaluation of the training activities, participants are required to assess such aspects as objective, time, performance and quality of the content.

Given the fact that agroecology is based on the three pillars (science, practice and movement), they are proposed as a basis for evaluation of the participants'. In other words, people participating in training on agroecological transition are asked to evaluate received learning outcomes from points of view of practice (questions 5 in Tab.2 and question a. below Tab. 2), science (questions 6, and question b. below Tab. 2) and movement (questions 7, and question c. below Tab. 2), as demonstrated in Table 2.

Table 2. Questions for evaluation of training activities by participants

N	Questions	Evaluation
1	How would you evaluate achieved goals (increased awareness of agroecological transition) of the performed training?	not achieved (1) – achieved (4)
2	How would you evaluate the quality of the content introduced during the training (its usefulness, appropriate focus, specific interest)?	not interesting/ useful/appropriate (1) - interesting/useful/appropriate (4)

3	How would you evaluate the training performance (process) from a participatory point of view?	Not participative (1) – Very participative (4)
4	How would you evaluate the time of the training activities?	Definitely not sufficient (1) - Sufficient (4)
5	How do you evaluate received practical skills related to agroecology and agroecological transition?	Definitely not useful (1) – Very useful (4)
6	How do you evaluate received scientific/theoretical knowledge related to agroecology and agroecological transition?	Definitely not useful (1) – Very useful (4)
7	How do you evaluate received knowledge and skills on movement building related to agroecology and agroecological transition?	Definitely not useful (1) – Very useful (4)

Open-ended questions:

- a) Could you specify at least 2-3 received practical skills that are most important/interesting to you?
- b) Could you specify at least 2-3 received scientific/theoretical knowledge that are most important/interesting to you?
- c) Could you specify at least 2-3 received skills on movement building that are most important/interesting to you?

Conclusion

Peasant farmers, agricultural workers and other rural peoples, are recovering their land and territories, preserving their culture and way of life on a daily basis. Those who committed to defend the Earth and to feed people, who carry out or desire to carry out peasant agroecological farming are the key actors to constructing food sovereignty.

Peasant farmers are considered as the main stakeholders that potentially will participate in future training programmes on agroecological transition. We hope this training guideline would encourage and make the path easier for the peasant farmers, for organising agroecology training programmes focused on fostering agroecological transition and contribute their advocacy efforts for better agroecological transition which supports peasant agroecology and small-scale agroecological farms.

Annexes

Annex 1. Agroecology training workshop

Brussels, 13 and 14 March 2023

Outcomes of the workshop (Annex 1) were used for development of the guidelines.

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Aims of the workshop and participants:

The workshop was organised in order to collect information on the methodology and pedagogy used in three training programmes which were carried out in the Netherlands, in the United Kingdom and in France in order to provide exhaustive information for the project Deliverable 4.4 - Training package guidelines. Along with the organisers of the training programmes in the AE4EU project, three additional participants from Spain (SLG and Ehne Bizkaia) and Belgium (Le MAP) who were not part of the project but members of European Coordination Via Campesina (ECVC) have been invited in order to create a larger space for more exchanges on the agroecology training programmes by peasant organisations and its methodology

The main goal of the workshop was to collect, to reflect on the main elements of the successful educational experience such as audience, contents, and used educational approaches. This was discussed during the first day of the workshop. Besides, the workshop was targeted at collecting ideas for a future potential agroecological training in ECVC, that was performed during the second day of the workshop.

Nine people (Tab. 1) and six interpreters have participated in the workshop.

Table 1. Participants of the workshop

N	Name	Organisation	Type of the stakeholder
1	Leonardo van den Berg	Toekomstboeren ¹⁴	Peasant organisation
2	Catherine Tellier	Le MAP ¹⁵ , L'EPI ¹⁶	Peasant organisation
3	Michele Roux	Confédération Paysanne ¹⁷ , FADEAR ¹⁸	Peasant organisation
4	Unai Aranguren	Ehne Bizkaia ¹⁹	Peasant organisation
5	Xose Maria Garcia Villaverde	SLG Galicia ²⁰	Peasant organisation
6	Hattie Richards	LWA ²¹	Peasant organisation

¹⁴ <https://toekomstboeren.nl/>

¹⁵ <https://www.lemap.be/>

¹⁶ <https://www.lemap.be/L-EPI-ecole-paysanne-independante>

¹⁷ <https://www.confederationpaysanne.fr/>

¹⁸ <https://www.agriculturepaysanne.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.ehnebizkaia.eus/>

²⁰ <http://sindicatolabrego.gal/>

²¹ <https://landworkersalliance.org.uk/>

7	Janneke Bruil (facilitator)	WUR, Cultivate Collective	Academia, Support organisation
8	Natalia Rastorgueva (facilitator)	University of Gastronomic Sciences (UNISG)	Academia
9	Olcay Bingol (facilitator)	ECVC	Peasant organisation

DAY 1 - 13.03.2023

1.1 Collective story harvest explanation

Collective Story Harvesting is an engaging and participatory process used to uncover a wealth of perspectives, insights, and dimensions that lie within the experiences of individuals, communities, teams, or organisations. This approach involves sharpening one's listening skills and focusing on specific predetermined details and topics during the storytelling process.

The aim of Collective Story Harvesting is to create a space where diverse voices are heard and valued, enabling a comprehensive exploration of a particular subject or theme. By actively listening and concentrating on specific aspects of the story, participants can unearth a rich tapestry of information, ideas, and emotions that may have been previously hidden or overlooked.

During this session at the workshop the process involved facilitators who guided the storytelling session in 3 break-out groups based on languages. They set the stage by establishing a safe and inclusive environment, ensuring that everyone feels comfortable sharing their stories. The facilitator also defined the focus areas to guide the participants' storytelling.

Once the storytelling began, participants were encouraged to share their experiences, narratives, and perspectives related to the training they have developed and practised. Each participant of the group took their turn to tell their story based on the questions asked by one of the members of the group. As they spoke, the facilitator and other participants actively listened, paid close attention to the specific details and took notes to be shared at the plenary.

The collected stories were then synthesised and analysed by the participants who are experts in their areas. Thus, six stories (successful educational experience) were shared by the participants from Toekomstboeren, Land Workers' Alliance, Ehne Bizkaia, SLG, FADEAR and Le MAP.

1.2 Audience selection and inclusion

This section provides bullet points that describe participants in each of six discussed educational experiences. In addition, lessons learnt are described at the end of this section.

1) Toekomstboeren story

- Training was aimed at farmers, researchers and activists
- Out of 37 participants, 14 were farmers
- Activists from different groups from all over country
- The diversity was fine and it was balanced. But there is a space for improvement (esp people of colour, LGBTQI)

2) Land Workers' Alliance story

- The training has been designed for those working with the land (farmers, growers, grazers, and new entrants), those who market, process or purchase food, and those who are engaged with farming and food research and policy making.
- 25 participants, working in different parts of the food system, mostly farmers

- Could do more to increase diversity (gender, people of colour) although it was quite well achieved
- Distance and timing is another challenge in relation to the growing season.

3) Ehne Bizkaia story

- First feminist agroecology school, only for and by women
- 16 young peasant women participated as learners. Bringing young women together gives a lot of joy.
- Women who are also producers shared their experiences in workshops which made them feel recognized and joyful.
- The participants perspectives and discussions influenced the organisation
- The participants stayed together and in solidarity after the training;
- Central approach: Young people and established (already) producers were linked.
- The main language spoken at the training was Basque, which was difficult for some people with a migration background. There is some work to do on intersectionality.

4) SLG story

- Different types of training programmes and forums:
 - Open farm days, visited mainly by young people who want to start a farm or learn about processing or selling.
 - Annual forum of two days (with talks and roundtables, most people come for 1 day). A great place to meet people from other similar experiences. Healing for the soul. It gives strength to continue to get out of your own place, your own everyday difficulties, and to meet people with fresh perspectives.
 - Specific training programmes on technical aspects related to, cattle grazing or cultivation. Some of these take place via zoom, which gives access to producers who cannot travel. They are sometimes spread over various days, for one or two hours per day.
 - School for peasant action, mostly for young people with a strong political content around the peasant voice and vision. This school specifically looks to maintain gender balance.
 - Training for feminist education, with workshops, visits etc. This has existed for many years already. The focus is not defined as agroecology per se but as ‘peasant farming with an agroecological orientation’. Topics can include the commons, seeds, mountain farming etc.
- Challenges in Galicia: people are spread apart, which makes training programmes that last several days much harder. And the producers also have different work schedules in their day.

5) FADEAR story

- FADEAR and its network were built around the Charter of Peasant Agriculture and around the training of peasants and militants of the Confédération Paysanne. They support farmers who want to improve their practices, develop the autonomy of their farm, the quality of their products or diversify their activity through advice but also short-format training, adapted to the work pace of farmers
- FADEAR in these training aimed to support participants who are farmers with the Peasant Farming Diagnosis tool. This allowed them to measure the situation of their farm with respect to smallholder agriculture using specific indicators and to define

their margins for improvement. It is also an opportunity to share with other farmers, to discover other practices and to gain perspective on the management of their farm. Farmers who are members of Confederation paysanne and their facilitators accompanied future farmers before their installation and provided them with support during the first years of their installation. The program was organised on 22 April with 20 farmers, peasant agriculture defenders, citizens and 2 May again 20 participants in the North of France. One day short course introduced the Diagnostic Tool and the history of peasant agriculture and also gave a chance to the participants to apply the tool in different farms as example during the visits of those farms during the course.

6) Le MAP L'EPI story

- L'Ecole Paysanne Indépendante is MAP's training centre, School for an agroecology school.
- The team of trainers is essentially made up of farmer-trainers and a few external trainers supporting the movement and the school.
- An essential tool for the analysis of agricultural practices is the Charter of Peasant Agriculture created in France by FADEAR.
- In addition to training, the EPI organises conferences, study sessions, visits, specialised course sessions, seminars, study trips and other knowledge exchange meetings as part of the agroecology school
- Challenge was that people come from different backgrounds and experiences.
- They divide the participants into different groups based on their experience and knowledge.
- One group was a farm school for the children of peasants with an agroecology background. One other group is doing farm visits with conversations about what is observed.

What was learnt in terms of the audience:

- We have to change the tools based on who we are aiming to reach. The content also needs to change based on the audience.
- Challenges:
 - Diversity, ensuring participation of different genders, cultures
 - Distance: sometimes it is too far to come together
 - Timing of the training: It is important in relation to farm work and seasons
 - Participants with different levels of knowledge and experience
- Most training programmes are for farmers, some on women, some on newcomers, on experienced farmers, or a mix. Sometimes also include producers in processing, marketing. armers, activists, researchers, but farmers in any combination should be in the centre.
- Establishing a political base is important, including with people from cities. Urban activists also contribute to make changes in the rural world but they have little understanding and do not know the reality and practices.
- Local or regional policy makers were not included in the educational activities . They are mostly included not as one of the trainees or experts but to do advocacy or to get information at the policy level.

- Organising excursions or events for municipalities, to bring them to dialogue spaces, e.g. on sanitary policies or including municipal policy officers who are responsible for regional food networks is important.

1.3 Content

This section describes the main topics of the training in the three educational experiences and summarises other experiences as lessons learnt.

1) Toekomstboeren story

- Main focus was agroecological transformation of food systems and the technical and political aspects were also included.
- Content: Decolonisation, sustainable, agroecological farming, land tenure, soil quality, no dig farming, movement building.
- Introduction on what is agroecology – political training for participants to understand why agriculture is political.
- For the decolonial part of the training they invited people who are active in the decolonial movement in the NL.
- Movement building: Focusing on Nyeleni Food Sovereignty movement in Europe. External people from the Nyeleni movement were invited and did farm visits and talked about strategies.

2) LWA story:

- Introducing agroecological approaches to developing farm and food systems that combine food production, environmental public goods, financial viability, and climate resilience.
- The training aimed to link agroecological principles with farming practices and processes that reduce reliance on external inputs and support the transformation of farming and food systems. The training also aimed to develop a firm understanding of agroecological principles and practices which can be used to analyse farming challenges and begin developing agroecological solutions to overcome them.
- Throughout the two days participants:
 - Explored various definitions and principles of agroecology
 - Considered how agroecological farming practices can help achieve objectives on farms
 - Gained skills in systems thinking to analyse farming problems and imagine solutions
 - Witnessed agroecological practices and systems in action at FarmED and Conygree Farm & Cotswold Market Garden
 - Learned the importance of the social, political and subtle dimensions of agroecology

3) EHNE Bizkaia story

- They adapted the language when concepts were unfamiliar, or too urban. They were not too purist. They could use ‘natural farming’ instead of agroecology.
- Three main topics:
 - 1) The rural woman as a political subject

- 2) Care for the earth and others
- 3) Public policy and law
- The practical part of agroecology was also included: how to make jam (processing agricultural products), processing dairy products, mill, flour and bakery , run a shop etc.

What was learnt in terms of content

- Most of the training programmes were related to production, processing, marketing, starting a farm, advanced techniques, and agroecological practices.
- Besides practical agroecological practices in all 3 training programmes and also the others always dedicated a part to Political-Ideological formation. One of the most important objectives of the agroecology training programmes is to bring in the practices and the political part based on our reality and connect us with others in the food systems and also with citizens. The practice should be contextualised by linking it to public policies at different levels. In order to build a political base to work on, it is important to make the connection from practical issues to the political aspects. All training programmes made it clear that practice is also political.
-
- Political-Ideological formation: Feminism, right and access to land, seed, water, seeds, water and other resources, regional and international processes, right of peasants
-
- Approach/ principles of agroecology should be included and based on Nyeleni agroecology declaration, FAO, HLPE 13 principles and lately ECVC's publication: Peasant Agroecology According to ECVC.

1.4 Pedagogies and educational approaches

This section describes learning process of the participants

1) Toekomstboeren story

- A methodology group coming from different working groups came together and designed the training. They also divided the tasks together. In order not to tire the participants they diversified the methods they used.
- Language: Dutch and English. When the international participants participated the training were done in English as all participants were fine with English.

Methods included:

- Rituals during the meeting and the dinner
- Classroom lectures
- Group work
- Circle discussions
- Videos
- Field trip
- Practical and theoretical training on soil and mechanisation for peasant farming
- Evening campfires with storytelling
- International speakers on movement building
- Political strategic discussions

- Background docs: Nothing was sent prior to the meeting but some resources were shared afterwards.
- The outcome of the training: Toekomstboeren is working to prepare a training curriculum to be used at the national level.

2) LWA story:

- Knowledge exchange and skill-share between farmers
- Co-creation of posters on: what is agroecology
- 'Pin the practice on the donkey' activity - participants take turns placing post-its describing their practices on the ESR framework.
- Each day starts with lecture, then group work, then field visit/ work, then group discussion with Q&A with 'expert'
- Day 1 started with lectures and group-work followed by exchange of information to understand where to see agroecology in their work. Agroecological practices were then observed during an on-farm walk, during field work and group discussions (farm talks with a specialist).
- Based on what was learnt on day 1, participants on day 2 created a systems map of the farm to address key issues the farmer raised during the walk.
- Storytelling, music making, and celebration are also part of the training even though they formally are the after-training times.
- Movement building and political agroecology was mostly addressed through lectures but may need some thinking on how to use other forms.
- Background documents: Some were sent before the training, some after.

3) Ehne Bizkaia story

- For three months, participants had the following schedule-
Tuesday: Theory (debate, round tables and presentations)
Thursday: Field visit to a producer to learn about a practice (cheesemaking, milling, jam making, etc.). They do a workshop and have a conversation afterwards. The producer first makes a presentation, then they work together. So there was theory and practice, as well as political and technical aspects.
- All teachers were also women, including the producers whom the participants visited . This allowed for a very good contact between established and new food entrepreneurs. An unexpected outcome was that the training also gave the established producers recognition.
- The group continued to be active after the training and recorded videos for March 8 International Women's Day on violence against women and on how women in the countryside are made invisible.
- Lesson 1: Women wanted more space to reflect among themselves., to reflect on what they learnt and saw together. And they wanted to visit each other's places also.
- Lesson 2: They brought international participants as resource people online, but doing it online did not work well.
- Lesson 3: Working on the topic of feminism and care also influenced the organisation as a whole.
- Lesson 4: Women who were professionals and had workshops were also made visible and lifted up.

- Lesson 5: The main language spoken at the training was Basque, which was difficult for some people with a migration background. There is some work to do on intersectionality.

4) FADEAR story

They match the learners with 3 farms (members of Confederation Paysanne) – to work in farms in a year.

An action-learning approach was used in involving people in peasant agriculture.

Classroom courses took place by the trainers

5) Le MAP story

It is important to use a clear and understandable language for all participants

Lessons learnt about educational approaches

- The methodologies and the content need to be adapted to the reality of the audience. Sometimes organising a dinner and bringing people to talk together is the best methodology. We have to organise methodologies that work for peasants.
- Finding the right mix is important because we want to get many different things out of a training programme. We want knowledge sharing, but also that farmers feel they are a collective. And that they are politicised, become political subjects. We want to connect to other movements. And we want them to feel energised to continue with the struggle.
- Learning the content is one of the outcomes of the training and the other is to make peasants feel connected to each other and to other movements.
- We want them to gain energy to continue their work and nourish their soul: Bringing people together to lift up people's spirits. That is why the fireplace, unstructured spaces, rituals and ceremonies are important.
- Some training programmes for and by a specific group eg women can be useful
- Terminology needs to be easy to understand, adapted to audience
- Online training works well for some sessions, esp when people cannot travel or have other duties
- There should always be a technical, political and movement building part
- Observation and analysis on-farm is very important

DAY 2 - 14.03.2023

After the intensive activities of the first day of the workshop, diverse information was collected and discussed. One of the main insights that came out during the 1st day was a future agroecology training programme potentially organised by ECVC (described in sections 2.1. and 2.2); another insight that came out during the workshop was a strong need in the training for trainers (described in section 2.3).

2.1 Reflections on a possible ECVC agroecology training programme

What should ECVC training programme guidelines look like? What are the principles, what is the content? It is agreed that there is no blueprint but a guideline, a manual for all ECVC to use can be developed collectively based on our values and approach to agroecology and training.

Reflections:

- Collection of the needs from the members is important.
- As ECVC, it is fundamental to develop training on training the trainers and organise those training programmes for them to disseminate and practise agroecology training on the field with members of their organisations.
- Translation of the tools in the main European languages are the key for a better reach-out and understanding..
- . The political content of the working groups should be used in the training and this allows the organisations to adapt the political content in their legislative and language realities. Those texts also would be very useful for integrating new members.
- EAKEN22 should be kept alive and should be regularly updated with members' resources and references on specific people on specific topics.
- We need to find a way and system (indexing and categorising) to collect all training documents and make them accessible.

2.3 Ideas on the Table of Contents for a Train the Trainer Document by ECVC

- Political context (information about policies; techniques, how to pursue struggles for rights for what they need). There should be a diagnosis on European political space along with international processes. European Union – structure - how it works - important legislation
- Content of the working groups: seeds, land, peasant agroecology, rural workers and migration, trade, etc
- Pedological-methodological aspect – how to facilitate in groups. Practices of Train the trainer- Facilitation skills; .
- Overview of key documents produced by ECVC and its members. An online library should be organised

²² <https://www.eaken.euovia.org/eaken/about-us/>

Annex 2. Reports of The Trainings Realised During AE4EU Project

To create guidelines for transformative agroecology learning, this report draws on three pilot training sessions with farmers, extension services, and/or other actors carried out in 2022 in three European countries: France (by FADEAR), the Netherlands (by Toekomstboeren) and the UK (by the Landworker's Alliance).

These training sessions were organised in order to reach a larger number of stakeholders in Europe and to show opportunities for development in agroecology and cooperation across Europe.

The three organisations that organised the trainings are:

- **Toekomstboeren²³** – a small-scale farmers association in the Netherlands and its name stands for “FARMERS FOR THE FUTURE”. Toekomstboeren gives to these farmers for the future a voice and supports them in their struggle;
- **FADEAR²⁴** (Fédération Associative pour le Développement de l'Emploi Agricole et Rural) – Associative Federation for the Development of Agricultural and Rural Employment; FADEAR and its network were built around the Charter of Peasant Agriculture and around the training of peasants and militants of the Confédération paysanne²⁵
- **LandWorkers' Alliance²⁶** - The Landworkers' Alliance is a union of farmers, growers, foresters and land-based workers. Its mission is to improve the livelihoods of our members and create a better food and land-use system for everyone.

The objective of these three training programmes was raising awareness of agroecological transformations and linking agroecological principles with farming practices.

The training programmes had a multi-actor approach. It means that the stakeholders with different roles such as farmers, researchers, representatives of NGOs, citizens, local authorities participated in the training programmes as trainees and as trainers (researchers, farmers, food producers, farmers organisations, social movements).

An action learning approach that has made a shift from theory towards “world” as the starting point for the learning process (Lieblein at al. 2010; Biesta, 2022) was used as a basis for training activities which included following:

- Practical information concerning agroecology
- Dialogue between the stakeholders

²³ <https://toekomstboeren.nl/>

²⁴ <https://www.agriculturepaysanne.org/>

²⁵ <https://www.confederationpaysanne.fr/>

²⁶ <https://landworkersalliance.org.uk/>

- Movement building

2.1.1 Toekomstboeren training (NL)

ECVC organised a training on agroecological transformation for young farmers, researchers and environmentalists with the support of Toekomstboeren on 14-16 May 2022 in the Netherlands in the framework of the AE4EU project.

On the 14th and 15th of May the training was given in De Merel (Woudenbergseweg 47, Austerlitz village, municipality of Zeist). On the 16th of May the training was held on the farm “Stadsboerderij Almere” (Kemphaanpad 14 in Almere). At the Merel participants were offered all meals and accommodation.

The training programme was attended by 37 people including 14 farmers, 9 researchers/students and 14 participants from environmentalist organisations or initiatives/collectives. Farmers came from different parts of the country both from farmers’ organisations as well as new entrant farmers. Researchers and students came mostly from Wageningen University although there were also researchers from applied knowledge institutes such as the Hanze Hogeschool. Environmentalists worked for organisations such as Greenpeace or were part of more activist groups such as Extinction Rebellion including participants of a professional artistic group.

Figure A. Training organised in the Netherlands

The main subject of the training was increased awareness of participants about agroecological transformation through four introduced topics: (i) decolonisation, (ii) land and commons, (iii) regenerative farming; (iv) movement building.

Each topic was discussed in a separate session during the training, that was taught and facilitated by an expert in the field. The first two training days focused on presenting basic knowledge of

each topic area. This was supported by guest speakers with specific experiences in practice, movement and/or policy.

The participants were first taken on a walk, led by forest and nature conservation professional Pablo van Neste (lecturer Wageningen University), who introduced the participants in the area and in the different species harboured by the forest surrounding the training location. This was followed by a collective dinner and a presentation of the programme of the training .

The first two training days were opened with a general introduction on agroecological transformation. Leonardo van den Berg (Toekomstboeren/Federation of Agroecological Farmers) outlined an overall framework on three areas of transformation: “practice, territory and the wider institutional environment”. Guest speaker Janneke Bruil focused on the governance aspect of agroecological transformation, looking at six governance domains: access to natural ecosystems, knowledge and culture, systems of exchange, networks, equity and discourse.

In addition Eduard Hernandez Nualart (Toekomstboeren/ECVC Youth) and Leonardo presented examples of transformative efforts by Nyeleni Food Sovereignty²⁷ movement, La Via Campesina²⁸ and Toekomstboeren.

After the session on “transformation” on the first day, Irma Brassinga (Toekomstboeren/Eet Meerbosch) led the session on Agroecology and Decolonization. With guest speakers Max de Ploeg (Aralez) a link was made between agroecology and decolonization and the necessity to reverse exploitative colonial relations between the global north and south as well as within agroecology itself.

This was followed by the session on “Land and Commons”. Margriet Goris (Agroecology Europe/Wageningen University) explained how the current situation, where many farmers do not have secure access to land, can be seen as result of the commoditization of land on the one hand and on imposed colonial relations between landlord and tenants on the other.

Eliane Bakker (Toekomstboeren/Lenteland) and Eduardo Cacades Salgado (Aralez) presented how “communing” initiatives are reversing these relations, by turning privately owned land into land that is owned and governed by the community.

The session ended with a closing ceremony called Trafkintu & Meli Witral Mapu, by Chatuileo Tranamil (Aralez) of the Mapuche Pewenche community. Until dinner participants had a chance to talk with speakers and discuss topics among themselves. After dinner Indigenous

²⁷ <https://nyeleni.org/en/homepage/>

²⁸ <https://viacampesina.org/en/>

leader Yuchen Li conducted a participatory performance called “Water as Memory, Bodies as Seed”.

On the second day of the training a session on “regenerative practices” was given. Frankie Turk (Re-peat) presented the problems of current industrial practices and how they are degrading soils, particularly peat lands.

Chris Chancellor (Tuinderij Het Lichtveen) gave an overview of agroecological farming practices and their capacity to regenerate the soil.

Gareth Hughes (FarmHack UK) presented Farm Hack, an initiative where farmers create their own, open source, equipment and machineries that are suited for agroecological farming. After lunch we conducted a hands-on, practical exercise on potting and making sustainable pot soil, led by Eduard Hernandez Nualart (Toekomstboeren) and Klarien Klingen (Toekomstboeren/De Wilde Peen).

The afternoon of the second day, started with “the movement building” session. Olcay Bingol international policy officer at the European Coordination of La Via Campesina (ECVC) and the technical secretariat of Nyeleni Europe and Central Asia Food Sovereignty Network) and Andrea Ferrante (Schola Campesina/Nyeleni ECA) presented Nyeleni Food Sovereignty movement as a movement capable of transformation at the global scale. Liz Knight (ASEED) presented local initiatives of the grassroots organisation ASeed.

2.1.2 FADEAR training (FR)

In France ECVC has organised the training program with the support of FADEAR in two days: on the 22th of April and on the 2nd of May in the North of France. Two different groups of 20 farmers have participated in training activities these days. The training was called: *"A better understanding of peasant agriculture: What is the place of agroecology in my project?"*

Training was open to farmers, citizens or defenders of peasant agriculture. The one-day event aimed to make the participants understand peasant thinking, its history, its link to agroecological approach and its direct application on farms.

During the training, a short course has introduced a Diagnostic Tool²⁹ and the history of peasant agriculture, detailed work specifically on 6 thematics of peasant agriculture based on

²⁹ *Diagnostic Tool: In the 90's the French farmers of the "Confederation paysanne" decided to work on a definition of an agriculture which could give an orientation to agricultural policies and to farmers to enable numerous farmers around the world to make a decent living from a sustainable agriculture that would keep the countryside alive. Together with academic researchers and based on their practices, they produced in 1998 a Charter with 10 principles and 6 main lines detailed in 84 indicators for a farm diagnosis*

the diagnostic tool and also gave a chance to the participants to apply the tool in different farms as example during the visits of those farms during the course.

Figure B. Training organised in France

The main objective of the training was to understand the peasant reflections, their link to an agroecological approach and its application on farms

Participating trainers:

- Willy Vindenvogel – Organic market gardener in peasant agriculture;
- Thomas Fayet – activist of peasant agriculture;
- Emilie Hequet - breeder in peasant agriculture;
- Marion Theriez – activist of peasant agriculture

The training was organised for following types of the invited stakeholders: farmers, project leaders, citizens and actors of peasant agriculture

Content:

- Creation and history of FADEAR;
- Peasant agriculture (definition, history, principles, themes);
- Agroecology (definition, link between agroecology and peasant agriculture, transition process);
- Case study (Willy Vindevogel) - Presentation of its farm diagnosis and the sustainability approach implemented on the farm;
- The Diagnostic tool.

2.1.3 Landworkers’ Alliance (LWA) training (UK)

In the UK, 25 participants attended the two-day short course which was organised by ECVC with the support of LWA on 30-31 May 2022, introducing agroecological approaches to developing farm and food systems that combine food production, environmental public goods, financial viability, and climate resilience. The training has been designed for those working with the land (farmers, growers, graziers, and new entrants), those who market, process or purchase food, and those who are engaged with farming and food research and policy making. Participated trainers: Jyoti Fernande, Gerald Miles, Jonathan Brunyee, Edd Colbert.

The training aimed to link agroecological principles with farming practices and processes that reduce reliance on external inputs and support the transformation of farming and food systems. The training also aimed to develop a firm understanding of agroecological principles and practices which can be used to analyse farming challenges and begin developing agroecological solutions to overcome them. Throughout the two days participants:

- Explored various definitions and principles of agroecology;
- Considered how agroecological farming practices can help achieve objectives on farms;
- Gained skills in systems thinking to analyse farming problems and imagine solutions;
- Witnessed agroecological practices and systems in action at FarmED and Conygree Farm & Cotswold Market Garden;
- Learned the importance of the social, political and subtle dimensions of agroecology.

Figure C. Training organised in the UK

As well as being inspired and gaining new knowledge from these two days the participants had a lot of opportunity to connect with other agroecologically minded participants in the classroom, over meals and around the campfire at Conygree Farm.

Throughout the two days of the training included a lot of group activities designed to support peer-learning and to encourage innovative thinking between folk from different walks of life. This required from the participants an open mind and a willingness to learn.

1.2. The Workshop in Brussels

The two-day in-person workshop was carried out in the office of ECVC (Brussels) in March 2023 (Fig. D). Three facilitators and six participants from different countries (Spain, France, Belgium, The UK, The Netherlands) and with different backgrounds discussed and shared training experiences. The workshop was carried out in three languages with simultaneous interpretation.

Figure D. Workshop in Brussels in March 2022

Collective story harvest (Møller et al. 2012) was used as a method for data collection. Collective story harvest includes strategic selection of listening themes, aimed at specific sense making. This method uses targeted listening to dig into the often-hidden learning in experience.

During the workshop six stories from the participants based on training experiences were shared and analysed (Annex 1). Besides, reflections for future training programmes by ECVC were collected:

- Linking training to the needs from the members is important;

- For ECVC, as a peasants' organisation, it is fundamental to develop training on “train the trainers”;
- All tools and documents need to be translated into the most spoken languages of Europe;
- The content of the different ECVC working groups should form the basis of the training programmes. Member organisations should be able to adapt the content to their needs and strategies (in education, policy, legislation, etc.). This content should also be useful to introduce new members to the issues ECVC works on;
- European Agroecology Exchange Network (EAKEN)³⁰ should function as a resource space for the development of national and European training programmes. EAKEN is a network aiming at linking initiatives in Europe which participate in the exchange of peasant agroecological knowledge based on the peasant to peasant methodology in ECVC needs to be more visible and also. For EAKEN, to function well, it should be updated regularly with members' resources and references on specific topics;
- A system (indexing and categorising) needs to be developed to collect all training documents and make them accessible for members. This system should be integrated in EAKEN
- Training programmes should have both political and practical content;
- Regular in-person training programmes for trainers should be prioritised.

In addition, proposals were collected for a future “Train the Trainers Document” that will be provided by ECVC and include following contents:

- Political context (information about what is agroecology in relation to food sovereignty and other topics, policies, etc.). Political context should be focused on the legal, administrative, political realities of Europe. The main question of the political content is: “How to change the society from the perspective of peasant values?”;
- The European Union, its structure and functions, important legislation for farmers;
- Content of the working groups of the ECVC: Peasant Agroecology, European Policies, Trade, Right to Land, Seed and Genetically Modified Organisms (GMOs), Rural Workers and Migration, Peasants' Rights, Youth, Women, Gender and Sexual Diversities;
- Pedagogical-methodological aspect;
- Overview of key documents produced by ECVC and its members. List of reference people in ECVC on key themes.

³⁰ <https://www.eaken.euovia.org/eaken/>